

1 **Does resistance training make a difference to the quality of life or heart health for older adults**
2 **compared to aerobic exercise? A systematic review protocol from The People's Review**

3 Éile Quinn^{1,2*}, Laura Bosner³, Patricia Logullo⁴, Kevin Murray⁵, KM Saif-Ur-Rahman^{2,6}, Charlene
4 Young⁷, Derek Stewart^{7,8}, Maureen Smith⁷, Jeremy Holt⁷, Shaun Treweek⁹ Chris Noone¹⁰, David
5 Moher¹¹, Sinéad M. Hynes¹ & The People.

- 6
- 7 1. Discipline of Occupational Therapy, School of Health Sciences, University of Galway, Galway,
8 Ireland.
 - 9 2. Evidence Synthesis Ireland and Cochrane Ireland, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland.
 - 10 3. School of Medicine, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland.
 - 11 4. Independent Researcher
 - 12 5. School of Pharmacy and Medical Sciences, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland.
 - 13 6. Centre for Health Research Methodology, School of Nursing and Midwifery, University of
14 Galway, Galway, Ireland.
 - 15 7. Public Partner
 - 16 8. HRB Trials Methodology Research Network, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland.
 - 17 9. Aberdeen Centre for Evaluation, University of Aberdeen, United Kingdom.
 - 18 10. School of Psychology, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland.
 - 19 11. Centre for Journalology, Methodological and Implementation Research, Ottawa Hospital
20 Research Institute, Ottawa, Canada

21 *Corresponding author. Éile Quinn, e.quinn34@universityofgalway.ie, Discipline of Occupational
22 Therapy, School of Health Sciences, Áras Moyola, University of Galway, University Road, Galway,
23 Ireland, H91TK33

24

25 **ABSTRACT**

26 **Background**

27 Systematic reviews bring together all the evidence on a health topic in an organised and careful way.
28 The People's Review aims to help the public understand what systematic reviews are and why they
29 matter by designing and conducting their own systematic review. The question chosen for The
30 People's Review is: *Does resistance training make a difference to quality of life and/or heart health*
31 *for older adults compared to aerobic exercise?* This paper outlines how we will carry out this review.

32 **Methods**

33 This is a systematic review involving the public throughout. This review will search for, include and
34 summarise:

- 35 • randomised controlled trials
- 36 • with older adults (50+ years)
- 37 • that compare resistance training (e.g. lifting weights) with aerobic exercise (e.g. walking or
38 running)
- 39 • and measure quality of life or heart health.

40 First, the technical team will search research databases to find possible studies. The public will look
41 at summaries of these to find studies that might be relevant. Then, two members of the technical
42 team will read the full studies and decide which ones to include. Next, the public will help collect
43 some of the key information from the included studies. The technical team will record the rest. The
44 public and the technical team will work together to check for biases (or flaws in how the studies were
45 done) in the studies. Finally, if possible, the team will combine the study results using a method
46 called meta-analysis (a way of pooling numbers together). If we can't combine the numbers, we will
47 write a summary of what the studies found.

48

49 **Discussion**

50 This review will summarise all the available evidence that addresses the review question. This
51 review could support the public to make decisions about what type of exercise to engage in as they
52 age, and influence exercise guidelines, clinical practice and future research.

53 **KEYWORDS**

54 Systematic review protocol; Citizen Science; Older adults; Resistance training; Aerobic exercise;
55 Evidence synthesis; Quality of life; Heart health; Cardiac outcomes

56

57 **INTRODUCTION**

58 This is a systematic review protocol from The People's Review – an online, novel citizen science
59 approach to involving members of the public in a systematic review. The overall aim of The People's
60 Review is to support the public in understanding what systematic reviews are and why they matter
61 (1). With this in mind, this protocol is written in plain English to make it accessible to as many
62 people as possible.

63

64 This protocol was produced with 366 members of the public, cited in this protocol as “the People”.
65 There is also a group of researchers and Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) contributors working
66 behind the scenes. Throughout this protocol, we refer to this group as the “Technical Team”. We are
67 all one large review team who have created this protocol together and will go on to produce a
68 systematic review together. We make this distinction throughout this protocol so that it is clear and
69 transparent who is doing what parts of the review.

70

71 **What this review is about: the importance of exercising**

72 As we age, our bodies change. Ageing gradually impacts our heart health and fitness. A decline in
73 heart health is closely linked to the onset of diseases, including heart failure (2), diabetes (3), and the
74 narrowing of arteries (4,5). Therefore, it is really important to find the best ways to support healthy

75 ageing in older adults, slowing the decline of heart health, preventing the onset of diseases, and
76 ultimately leading to a better quality of life (6).Regular exercise has a positive impact on healthy
77 ageing (7,8). Exercise prevents the onset of disease, maintains function, improves mental health, and
78 brings social benefits. In particular, regular exercise supports heart health for older adults (9–11).

79

80 **Types of exercise we will investigate**

81 Different types of exercise are promoted to improve heart health, quality of life, muscle strength,
82 mobility and many other outcomes (10–12). Aerobic exercise is an activity that increases the heart
83 rate and breathing, while engaging large muscle groups over a sustained period. These exercises
84 improve heart health, fitness and endurance. Examples include brisk walking, running, swimming,
85 cycling, or dancing. Resistance training is another form of exercise that involves using external force
86 or load to challenge and strengthen muscles. The external force could be lifting weights, pulling
87 against elastic resistance bands, or using one’s body weight to work against gravity.

88

89 Traditionally, aerobic training was recommended as the best form of exercise to support heart health
90 (10,12,13). However, in recent years, emerging research suggests that resistance training may also
91 play an important role in improving heart health (14–17). Although the main goal of resistance
92 training is to increase muscle strength (18), the American Heart Association (AHA) recommends
93 engaging in regular resistance training to lower the risk of heart disease and maintain a healthy heart
94 (19).

95

96 However, there is still uncertainty about how resistance and aerobic training compare to each other
97 for supporting heart health (20) and quality of life (21). A recent systematic review explored the
98 effects of aerobic versus resistance training on heart health in older adults (22). However, that review
99 did not focus on quality of life, and had several limitations. Therefore, it is still unclear whether

100 resistance training makes a difference to the quality of life and heart health for older adults compared
101 to aerobic exercise. This review will compare these two types of exercise: resistance and aerobic
102 training.

103

104 **How resistance training might improve heart health and quality of life**

105 Resistance training causes a person's blood pressure to lower, meaning there is less pressure put on
106 the heart as it pumps blood around the body (15,16). There is also an increase in the amount of blood
107 the heart can hold and pump out with each beat, meaning the heart works more efficiently (17). The
108 ability for blood vessels and the body's muscles and cells to transport and use oxygen is improved
109 through resistance training, therefore reducing the effort on the heart to supply oxygen (23–25).

110 Resistance training can lower cholesterol, balance blood sugars and reduce body fat, which can
111 impact heart health (14,26). Through these effects, resistance training has been shown to reduce the
112 risk of developing heart disease (19).

113

114 Resistance training may improve more than just heart health for people over the age of 50. It can also
115 enhance overall physical health (27,28), lower the risks of falls (29), and improve mental health in
116 older adults (21,30–32). Any type of physical activity can improve quality of life (33), including
117 resistance training, as likely due to the release of feel-good chemicals in the brain and strengthening
118 pathways in the brain that control our emotions and mood [35–37]. Additionally, resistance training
119 can help older adult's brain function (34) such as concentration and memory.

120

121 **Why it is important to do this systematic review**

122 Finding out whether resistance training is equally good or better than aerobic exercise may be useful
123 to the public, healthcare workers (such as doctors, nurses, or physiotherapists), policymakers, and

124 researchers to inform recommendations about what older people can do to support their physical and
125 mental well-being.

126

127 Perhaps the most important reason for conducting this systematic review is that the question was
128 selected by the public. Through three rounds of priority-setting surveys, the People decided the final
129 question for this review.

130

131 **What is the aim of this review?**

132 This systematic review aims to find out if resistance training makes a difference to quality of life
133 and/or heart health for older adults (aged 50 years or older) compared to aerobic exercise.

134 **METHODS**

135 This is a systematic review protocol with public involvement throughout. This protocol follows the
136 PRISMA-P reporting checklist (35). It is important to follow this checklist so that the protocol is
137 clear, complete and easy for everyone to understand. This protocol is registered in PROSPERO:
138 CRD420251156252. See Fig. 1 for an overview of the methods.

What is a systematic review protocol?

A systematic review protocol is a plan for how a systematic review will be done. A protocol should be written up and shared *before* the authors of the review begin searching for and analysing the studies to be included in the review. A systematic review protocol improves the quality of the review, holds authors accountable to the set out plan, and allows others to take a look at the work before it starts (36).

139 **Fig 1. A flow diagram of this systematic review’s methods** What studies will we include in our
 140 **review?**

141

142 **What type of studies will we include in our review – the eligibility criteria?**

143 A study will be included in this systematic review if it:

- 144 1. Is a randomised controlled trial (RCT)
- 145 2. Includes people over the age of 50
- 146 3. Compares resistance training with aerobic exercise
- 147 4. And measures quality of life and/or heart health

148 The study must meet all four of these criteria in order for it to be included in the review. Each of
149 these are described in further detail below.

150

151 ***Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) only – the study design***

152 We will only include randomised controlled trials (RCTs) in our review. Randomised trials are
153 widely considered the most reliable way to evaluate whether healthcare interventions work or not.

154 We will include all types of randomised trials, including the traditional and simple ones (like those
155 with two or more groups) and more sophisticated designs, such as cluster-randomised trials (where
156 participants are randomised in a cluster or group, such as by clinic or nursing home unit) and cross-
157 over trials (where participants are randomly assigned to either the resistance training or aerobic
158 exercise group and then switched). All other types of studies will be excluded from our review.

159

160 ***Older adults – the population***

161 We define older adults as people over the age of 50. Trials with people aged 49 years or younger will
162 be excluded from our review. If a trial includes both people over 50 and under 50, we will include it
163 only if the data for people over 50 is reported separately.

164

165 There is some disagreement in the literature about what we mean by an ‘older adult’ (37,38). For
166 example, the World Health Organization defines older adults as people over the age of 60 (6). Others

167 argue that older adults include people over the age of 50, especially where life expectancy is lower
168 (39,40). For this review, the People decided to focus on adults over the age of 50.

169

170 ***Resistance training and aerobic exercise – the intervention and comparator***

171 We will include trials that compare resistance training with aerobic exercise. For our review, we
172 consider resistance training to be the main intervention being studied and aerobic exercise to be the
173 comparator. We define resistance training as a form of exercise that involves using external force or
174 load to challenge and strengthen your muscles. The external force could be lifting weights, pulling
175 against elastic resistance bands, lifting weighted objects (such as bricks or bottles of water), or using
176 your own body weight (such as squats, or push-ups).

177

178 We define aerobic exercise as any activity that increases heart rate and breathing, while engaging
179 large muscle groups over a sustained period. These exercises improve heart health, fitness and
180 endurance. Examples include brisk walking, running, swimming, cycling, dancing, or sports. The
181 People decided these definitions of resistance training and aerobic exercise.

182

183 We will include trials that compare resistance training with aerobic exercise where the programme
184 includes at least eight sessions (as chosen by the People). Trials with fewer than eight sessions will
185 not be included in the review.

186 ***Quality of life and/or heart health – the outcomes***

187 We are interested in two main outcomes for this review: quality of life and heart health. Therefore,
188 we will include trials that measured either quality of life or heart health (and compare resistance
189 training with aerobic exercise).

190

191 Quality of life refers to a person's overall satisfaction with their life, involving the interaction
192 between their physical health, emotional well-being, independence, social relationships, and the
193 environment. We will use the World Health Organisation's definition of quality of life as
194 "individuals' perceptions of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in
195 which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns" (41).

196

197 Quality of life is usually measured using specially-designed questionnaires. Some commonly used
198 questionnaires to measure quality of life include the Short-Form 36 (42,43), EuroQol (44), and the
199 WHOQOL (45).

200

201 We will use functional fitness as the measure for heart health. Functional fitness (or functional
202 aerobic capacity) is a person's ability to keep exercising over a sustained time period, at a level
203 where they can still talk without becoming very breathless. It is one of the best measures of overall
204 fitness and heart health as it evaluates all the body's systems working together during exercise
205 (46,47). We will include studies that measure functional fitness through accepted tests such as the 6-
206 minute walk test (6MWT), shuttle tests or other methods.

207

208 No other outcomes will be explored in this review. We acknowledge that this review could focus on
209 many other outcomes related to heart health. However, the People decided to focus only on
210 functional fitness, as this was considered the most important measure of heart health for them.

211

212 **How will we search for the studies for our review? – the search strategy**

213 *Searching for the studies in electronic databases*

214 We will develop a search strategy with the help of a medical librarian and following best practice for
215 developing, testing and reporting search strategies (48,49). The search strategy will be independently
216 peer-reviewed.

217

218 To search for relevant studies, we will combine three concepts:

- 219 • The population - ‘older adults’(using the filter by for people over the age of 50 (50)).
- 220 • The intervention - ‘resistance training’
- 221 • The comparator – ‘aerobic exercise’
- 222 • The study design – ‘randomised controlled trials’ (using the Cochrane filter (51)).

223 For each concept, we will search for different words and subject headings related to the concept and
224 then combine the three concepts. For further details of our search strategy, please see Appendix 1.

225

226 We will search online databases that contain millions of studies from around the world. To make
227 sure we capture the breadth of research, we searched the following databases:

- 228 • MEDLINE Ovid
- 229 • Embase Ovid
- 230 • PsycINFO
- 231 • CINAHL
- 232 • PEDro
- 233 • LILACS
- 234 • Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL)

235 We will not limit the search by language of publication or publication date.

236

237 ***Searching for the studies in other places***

238 It is not enough to only search online databases of finished and published trials, as some trials could
239 be missed. Therefore, we will search for ongoing trials on the US National Institutes of Health
240 Ongoing Trials Register ClinicalTrials.gov (<https://www.clinicaltrials.gov>) and the World Health
241 Organisation International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP;
242 <https://www.who.int/tools/clinical-trials-registry-platform>).

243

244 Sometimes studies may also be missed because they are not published in journals. For example, there
245 could be valuable information in government reports, conference presentations, pre-print servers,
246 theses or dissertations. This is known as grey literature. To try and find grey literature, we will use
247 the same search terms in ProQuest Dissertations and Theses Citation Index via the Web of Science
248 and the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) Data Station, which allows access to all
249 records in greynet.org and all other records previously hosted on the System for Information on Grey
250 Literature database. We will also search medRxiv, the pre-print server for health sciences
251 (<https://www.medrxiv.org/>).

252

253 Additionally, we will look at the reference lists of the included studies to find trials that may not be
254 brought up by the searches. We will also see which newer studies have cited them to make sure we
255 don't miss any important studies. Finally, we will check the reference lists of similar systematic
256 reviews (22,30) published on this topic also.

257 **How will we select the studies for our review? – screening**

258 As we will search across multiple databases, some studies will likely be included in more than one
259 database, and we will need to remove these duplicates. The Technical Team will use Rayyan (52) to
260 remove the duplicates.

261 We will then select the studies for our review in two steps, in a process known as screening. We will
262 report the process on how we selected the studies using a flow diagram (35), clearly outlining the
263 number of studies that made it through each round.

264

265 ***Step 1: Title and abstract screening***

266 In the first round of the screening process, the public will decide whether studies are relevant for our
267 review by looking at the titles and abstracts of potential studies and deciding if they are ‘Possibly
268 relevant’ or ‘Not relevant’. Each abstract will be screened by at least four members of the public. If
269 there is a discrepancy, a member of the Technical Team will act as a resolver to make the final
270 decision about whether it should make it through the next round of screening, full-text screening.
271 This process has been previously described in The People's Review project protocol (1,53,54).

272

273 ***Step 2: Full-text screening***

274 Two members of the Technical Team will read the full texts of all abstracts that the People screened
275 as relevant for this review. Reading the complete versions of the studies will allow the team to
276 confirm whether they should be included in the review (or not). If these two team members have
277 different opinions, they will discuss until agreeing. If agreeing about including the study is too
278 difficult, they will consult with a third member of the team to decide.

279 **How will we collect the information from the studies? – data extraction**

280 The People will extract some pieces of information from the studies, and the Technical Team will
281 pull out others. The People will look for information about the participants (for example, number of
282 people who took part in the trial, their age, gender/sex, disability, location of the study), the
283 intervention/comparator (for example, details about the number of sessions, description of the

284 exercise and comparator) and outcomes (what was measured and how). The team will extract all
285 other information, including results data.

286

287 The People can extract information from as many studies as they wish, but we ask that they extract
288 information at least one study each. The included studies will be assigned to four individuals
289 randomly. Therefore, each study will have its data extracted by four different members of the public.

290

291 The remaining data, mainly about the trial results, will be collected from the studies by two
292 independent members of the Technical Team. For both the People and the Technical Team, the data
293 will be collected from the studies using a data extraction form that will be designed for this study,
294 pilot-tested, and implemented online.

295

296 Just like for the screening, it is possible that the data collected from the same study by two or more
297 people may not match. When this happens and there is less than 80% agreement for each data item
298 extracted by the People, a resolver from the Technical Team will make the final decision. If the
299 Technical Team members do not agree, this disagreement will be resolved through discussion, or
300 involving a third team member if necessary.

301

302 If reported in the studies the following information will be extracted (between the People and the
303 Technical Team). This will include information about:

304

- 305 • the study itself, including: the study/report ID, year of publication, journal, authors and
306 funding

- 307 • the participants in the trial, including: age, sex, gender, sexual identity, race, ethnicity or
308 ancestry, socio-economic status, level of education, disability, and residence (country and
309 type, if rural/urban).
- 310 • the intervention groups: description of both the resistance and aerobic trainings provided,
311 where training took place, who delivered or supervised the training, exercising duration (how
312 long) and frequency (how many).
- 313 • the outcomes: quality of life or functional fitness, how these outcomes were measured and
314 defined, and the units of measurement.
- 315 • the results, including: the number of participants allocated to the intervention and the
316 comparison groups, number of participants included in the analysis.

317

318 **How will we check for bias in the studies? – risk of bias**

319 An important step in a systematic review is checking if there are any potential flaws (known as bias)
320 in how the studies were done, how these flaws may have impacted the results, and therefore
321 influence how much or how little we can trust the study. We call this risk of bias. To measure the
322 trials’ risk of bias, we will use Cochrane’s risk of bias tool (55). This tool looks at seven different
323 aspects (called domains) of the randomised trial process. These domains are described in table 1.

324

325 **Table 1. What do we look at when checking for the risk of bias in trials?**

Domain	What it is	Why it matters	Timing
<i>Random sequence generation</i>	The way researchers ensure the assignment of participants to the intervention and comparison groups happen at random. For example, by flipping a coin, rolling a dice, or	Randomising participants to each group makes sure the researchers do not choose who goes into what group. It also ensures the groups are similar from the beginning and the distribution is fair (for example, with groups that are roughly the same size	At the beginning of the trial before participants are being placed into the intervention or comparison group.

	using a computer programme.	and with similar characteristics).	
<i>Allocation concealment</i>	Making sure the people enrolling participants do not know or cannot predict which group the participant will be assigned to. This domain is about the method used to hide the allocation.	It is important that the people running the trial are not be able to influence which treatment each participant gets. For example, if the person enrolling a participant knows that the next assignment is to intervention group (consciously or unconsciously) assign a participant they think will do better in the intervention group.	At the beginning of the trial, before and during the randomisation process.
<i>Blinding of participants and personnel</i>	Making sure that both the participants receiving either the intervention or comparator (the participants), and the people running the trial (the personnel) are unaware of which group participants are in.	Participants and/or the people running the trial might act differently if they know whether participants are getting the intervention or comparison.	During the trial when the participants are receiving the intervention or comparison.
<i>Blinding of outcome assessors</i>	Making sure that the people measuring the outcomes are unaware which group participants are in.	If the outcome assessor knows whether the participant is in the intervention or comparison group they might change the outcome to make the results more favourable.	When the outcomes are measured (usually before and after the intervention)
<i>Incomplete outcome data</i>	When there is missing data because participants may have dropped out of the trial, or did not complete all of the outcome measures. This domain looks at how much data is missing and if it was handled properly.	It is normal to have some missing information in trials. But if there is lots of missing information especially in one group and not another, it can influence the trial results.	When the results of the trial are being analysed.
<i>Selective reporting</i>	Whether the researchers reported all the results they	Leaving out results that researchers didn't like can give a false impression of	Happens when the results of the trial are being written

	planned to in the protocol.	how well something worked.	up and published.
<i>Other bias</i>	This is a place to note any other problems that may have influenced the results of the trial; for example, conflicts of interest, not following the plan, or stopping the trial early.	Sometimes there are problems that don't fit neatly into the other domains.	At any stage during the trial.

326

327 For each domain, we will assign a judgement of either low risk of bias, high risk of bias or some
328 concerns. As previous stages, the public can assess the risk of bias in as many studies as they choose;
329 however, they will be asked to assess the risk of bias in at least one study.

330

331 The public will look at the first four risk of bias domains, with the remaining three domains to be
332 assessed independently by two members of the Technical Team. Each study will be assessed by at
333 least four different members of the public. If there is less than 80% agreement by the members of the
334 public about the risk of bias judgement, a member of the Technical Team will act as a resolver to
335 make the final decision. If discrepancies arise in the Technical Team, they will resolve it through
336 discussion or with a third assessor.

337

338 If cluster randomised trials are included, the Technical Team will assess all seven risk of bias
339 domains for these trials. This is because cluster randomised trials require additional considerations,
340 such as whether the analysis accounts for clusters, whether effects are overestimated, or if there were
341 recruitment issues (56).

342

343 The results from the public’s assessment and the Technical Teams’ assessment will be combined and
344 summarised in tables and graphs. We will also summarise the risk of bias within each study in a
345 table.

346 How will we analyse and summarise the results from each trial?

347 Once we have extracted the data from the included trials and assessed them for risk of bias, we will
348 then synthesise the results. Synthesising means carefully combining the results data from all the
349 individual trials to provide an overall picture of the evidence.

350

351 In systematic reviews that compare two treatments, we typically use a statistical method known as
352 meta-analysis to synthesise numerical data. Meta-analysis combines the results data from each
353 individual trial and produces a summary, or overall result. The result of synthesising the data using
354 meta-analysis produces a graph called a forest plot (described in Fig. 2).

355 **Fig. 2. What is a forest plot?**

356

357 Sometimes it is not always appropriate or possible to do a meta-analysis and produce a forest plot. In
358 this case, we will use other ways (57) to summarise the results, including words and tables.

359
360 ***Measuring the effects of the intervention versus the comparator***

361 We want to find out how resistance training compares to aerobic exercise on quality of life and heart
362 health (measured by functional fitness). To do this, we must calculate the difference between the
363 intervention and the comparator. What calculation we use is based on two factors: 1) the type of data
364 we are working with, and 2) whether the studies measure the outcomes in the same way.

365
366 The type of data for both of our outcomes, quality of life and heart health, is continuous. Continuous
367 outcomes are based on scales with values that are in a specified range – everyday examples of
368 continuous data include height, weight, and temperature.

369
370 We will use either the mean difference or the standardised mean difference to measure the difference
371 between the two groups. If the outcomes are measured in the same way in all trials, using the same
372 test, we will calculate the mean difference and 95% confidence interval. Mean difference is the
373 average difference between the two groups.

374

How to calculate mean difference – a worked example

Say people doing resistance training rate their quality of life as 70 out of 100. People who do aerobic exercise rate it as 65 out of 100. The mean difference would then be 5. A 95% confidence interval is the range of numbers that is likely to include the true mean difference. For example, if resistance training improves quality of life by 5 points more than aerobic exercise, with a confidence interval of 3-7 points, this suggests the real

difference is likely between 3 and 7. The 95% confidence interval means that if we repeated the study 100 times, in 95 of those studies, the range we would find (like 3-7 points) would include the true mean difference.

375

376 If the outcomes are not measured in the same way, using the same scale (which is quite likely for
 377 both quality of life and functional fitness), we will calculate the standardised mean difference. For
 378 example, one study might score quality of life out of 10, and another out of 100. The standardised
 379 mean difference puts all the results on the same scale, so we can still compare them fairly.

380 ***How will we account for problems with study designs that may affect the results? – unit of analysis***
 381 ***issues***

382 Data collected in randomised trials should be analysed in ways that match how the data was
 383 collected. For simple trials where each participant is randomly allocated to either the intervention or
 384 the comparator, there are usually no issues. However, for more sophisticated trial designs there are
 385 some considerations that we need to make, to ensure that we do not over or underestimate the effects
 386 of the intervention. These considerations are described in table 2.

387

388 ***Table 2. Study designs that need to be accounted in this review***

Randomised trial designs	Explained	What we will do about these designs in this review
Randomised trials with more than two groups	For example, one group of participants could do resistance training, another could do aerobic exercise, a third could do both resistance training and aerobic exercise.	We will extract data only from the resistance training group and the aerobic exercise group. We will not analyse data from combined interventions (for example interventions that use aerobic and resistance training).
Crossover trials	Where participants are randomly assigned to either resistance training (the intervention) or aerobic exercise (the comparator). Then the groups swap and do the other exercise type. However, the	To prevent the impact of the carryover effect we will use the results from the first period before the groups swap.

	effects of the first type of exercise might still be there when people start the second type. That makes it harder to tell which exercise is really causing the results.	
Cluster randomised trials	When participants are randomised in a cluster or group, such as by clinic, school or nursing home.	The Technical Team will assess if the authors of the cluster trials have appropriately accounted for clustering and get advice from a statistician if needed. If the authors have not appropriately accounted for clusters, we will adjust for this using methods recommended in the Cochrane handbook (58).

389

390 ***What will we do if there is information missing that we need? – dealing with missing data***

391 It is common for trials not to report all the information needed for a review. If this happens, we will
392 initially contact the trial authors to request the missing information. We will record the amount of
393 missing data, specify what data is missing, and the reasons for missing data (if known). If the authors
394 have filled in missing data by using estimated guesses (known as imputation), we'll decide if the
395 approach is appropriate based on best practice (59).

396

397 If the authors do not respond to us with the missing data, the Technical Team may use accepted
398 methods to estimate the missing values (known as imputation). For example, if standard deviations
399 (which show how spread out the results are from the average) are missing and cannot be calculated
400 from the data, the Technical Team will follow Furukawa's guidance on imputing this data (60). We
401 will only fill in missing values if there is a small amount (less than 10%) of data missing. If there are
402 large amounts of missing data, we will exclude this from the meta-analysis (the statistical method of
403 combining the results). We will, however, include the trials in our review and summarise them in
404 writing. We will make note of any missing data and discuss the potential impact of this on the results
405 of our review in the discussion section.

406

407 **How will we assess whether the studies are similar or different to each other? - heterogeneity**

408 Heterogeneity is the extent to which the trials are different from each other. It is important to check
409 how different the trials are so we have a clear picture of the evidence. There are also practical
410 reasons for the review because if they vary too much, combining the results in a meta-analysis
411 (shown in a forest plot) could give misleading results. In systematic reviews, heterogeneity can be
412 measured in several ways. Each test is different and has strengths and weaknesses. We will use three
413 different tests to account for these limitations. The Technical Team will conduct all three tests, and
414 the People will help interpret the results of the tests.

415

416 For our review, we will first look closely at the forest plot produced from the meta-analysis. We will
417 look out for:

- 418 1. The point estimate distribution
- 419 2. Overlapping confidence intervals
- 420 3. The width of the confidence intervals

421 These concepts are explained further in Fig. 3.

422 **Fig. 3. Visually inspecting a forest plot**

LESS HETEROGENEITY

- The trials appear to be quite similar because:
- The point estimate's are close together and mostly on the left side.
 - All confidence intervals are overlapping.
 - The confidence intervals are relatively narrow.

MORE HETEROGENEITY

- The trials appear to be quite different because:
- The point estimate's are far apart close and on either side of the line.
 - Most of the confidence intervals are not overlapping.
 - The confidence intervals are quite wide.

423

424 After visually inspecting the forest plot, we will also measure the heterogeneity using a calculation
425 called the I^2 estimate, which is represented as a percentage (%). We will use the thresholds outlined
426 in table 3 (61). There is overlap across the thresholds, as I^2 estimates should be interpreted cautiously
427 based on the context.

428

429 **Table 3. I^2 estimate thresholds**

Threshold	Meaning
75-100%	Considerable heterogeneity - meaning the studies may be very different from each other
50-90%	Substantial heterogeneity - meaning the studies may be somewhat different from each other.
30-60%	Moderate heterogeneity - meaning there is some difference that may be important.
0-40%	The studies are fairly similar and the amount of difference is possibly not relevant.

430

431 We will also complete a statistical calculation called the chi squared test. The chi squared test can
432 assess whether the difference between the studies is due to chance alone or for other reasons. It is
433 presented as a number called p-value. The lower the p-value (the closer to zero), the higher the
434 probability that the heterogeneity is likely not due to chance and is statistically significant (61).

435

436 We will summarise our assessment of heterogeneity in a written summary, including possible causes
437 of heterogeneity. If we observe high levels of heterogeneity, indicating that the studies are too
438 dissimilar to pool together, we will not complete a meta-analysis. Performing a meta-analysis of
439 trials that are too different would not be appropriate and may misrepresent the study's results. We
440 will report the results in this case in written and table format, following best practice guidelines (57).

441

442 ***How will we check if trials are missing? - assessment of reporting biases***

443 A common problem with research is that sometimes trials with less favourable results are simply not
444 published at all and the results are hidden from the public. This is known as reporting bias. Reporting

445 bias can impact the results of a systematic review, as it might seem like one treatment (the one with
446 more published trials) is more effective than it actually is.

447

448 To check for reporting bias, we will follow the guidance in the Cochrane Handbook (62). We will
449 use a funnel plot if there are more than 10 studies included in our meta-analysis (63,64). A funnel
450 plot (Fig. 4) can be used to explore whether reporting bias is present. If the funnel plot's shape is
451 symmetrical, then this indicates an absence of reporting bias. If it is asymmetrical, then this suggests
452 that results are grouped, telling "one side" of the story, or showing only the positive findings - there
453 may be some reporting bias or hidden results, and, therefore, missing evidence. Besides analysing the
454 plot visually, we will check for funnel plot asymmetry using a statistical test called an Egger test
455 (65). The Technical Team will prepare the funnel plot and complete the Egger test, and the People
456 will help interpret the funnel plot.

457 **Fig. 4. How to interpret a funnel plot**

SYMMETRICAL FUNNEL PLOT

Suggests that there is no reporting bias.

ASYMMETRICAL FUNNEL PLOT

Suggests that there may be some reporting bias, and therefore missing evidence.

458

459 ***How will we combine the results from each study together? - Data synthesis***

460 If the studies are sufficiently similar, they will be combined using meta-analysis. We will perform a
461 separate meta-analysis for each outcome – quality of life and heart health (measured by functional

462 fitness). We will use a website called MetaAnalysisOnline.com (66) to conduct the meta-analysis as
463 it is freely available and open access.

464

465 One member of the Technical Team will enter the data into MetaAnalysisOnline.com and another
466 will check that the data was inputted accurately. The meta-analysis will then be conducted in two
467 steps.

468

- 469 • Step 1: Calculate the measure of effect for each study using either the mean difference or
470 standardised mean difference (as described in the section: *Measuring the effects of the*
471 *intervention versus the comparator*).
- 472 • Step 2: Combine the effect measures using the random-effects model using the inverse-
473 variance methods. There are different types of statistical models to use for a meta-analysis –
474 we will use the random-effects model because it takes into consideration any difference
475 (heterogeneity) across the studies.

476 If meta-analysis is not appropriate, for example, if there are lots of missing data, or if the studies are
477 very different from each other, then we will describe the results through written word, tables, and
478 graphs. We will follow best practice guidelines for explaining the results in this way – this guidance
479 is known as SWiM (Synthesis without meta-analysis; (57).

480 ***Will we look at groups of studies with specific aspects? - Subgroup analysis***

481 As decided by *the People*, we will conduct a sub-group analysis to explore differences:

- 482 • Across sex and/or genders (based on what is most commonly reported in the trials).
- 483 • In age categories between 50-60 years and 60+ years.
- 484 • Between healthy participants and participants with reported health conditions.

485

486 *How will we explore whether studies with high risk of bias made a difference to the results? -*
487 *sensitivity analysis*

488 A sensitivity analysis will explore the influence of studies with a high risk of bias in any domain. We
489 will achieve this by excluding studies with a high risk of bias from the analysis and examining the
490 differences in the overall results. This will be done using MetaAnalysisOnline.com (66), and it will
491 be reported in a table, or forest plot. If cluster randomised trials are included, we will also conduct a
492 sensitivity analysis excluding the studies that did not account for clustering in their analysis.

493 *How will we determine how sure we can be that resistance training makes a difference to the*
494 *quality of life or heart health for older adults compared to aerobic exercise? - assessment of the*
495 *certainty of evidence*

496 In a systematic review, we determine how confident we can be in the results or how sure we are that
497 the evidence gathered by the review is a good representation of the likely effect of the intervention
498 (resistance training). This is called certainty of evidence. (67).

499
500 To assess the certainty of evidence for our review, we will use the GRADE (Grading of
501 Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation) approach (68). GRADE uses a
502 transparent and organised approach to rating the certainty of evidence in four categories: high,
503 moderate, low and very low certainty of evidence.

504
505 For the GRADE approach, if all the studies are randomised trials, then we start with high certainty of
506 evidence. However, the rating can decrease if there are issues. GRADE looks at five domains which
507 may lead to reducing the certainty of evidence:

508

509 ***Table 3. Domains that can rate down the certainty of evidence in the GRADE approach***

Domain	What it is	Why it matters	How it is assessed
--------	------------	----------------	--------------------

Risk of bias	There are flaws in how the studies were done.	If the studies were not well done and there is a high risk of bias, the results may be less reliable (69).	Using the risk of bias assessment described in section: <i>How will we check for bias in the studies? – risk of bias</i>
Imprecision	When the studies have very small numbers of participants, or the confidence intervals are very wide.	If the results are too imprecise we cannot be confident in the size of the effect (70).	Checking the width of the confidence interval if the effect size (usually the diamond in the forest plot) and by asking ourselves do we have enough participants overall to be confidence in the results?
Indirectness	When the studies don't exactly match the question of interest (e.g., different population, interventions or outcomes).	If the evidence doesn't directly address the question we're asking, it is not very useful for answering it (71).	By looking at the population, interventions and outcomes in the studies and asking ourselves do these match the review question?
Inconsistency	When the studies give very different results.	If the studies give very different results it is much harder to know whether the intervention actually works or not (72).	By checking if studies show similar results in both direction and size, and by using statistical tests (like I ²) to measure how much they differ.
Publication bias	When there are studies missing (usually those showing no effect or negative results)	If only certain results are available, the evidence may only be telling one side of the story and show misleading results (69).	Using a funnel plot (and statistical tests for asymmetry) as described in the section: <i>Assessment of reporting bias</i> .

510

511 Both outcomes, quality of life and heart health (measured by functional fitness), will be assessed
512 using this GRADE approach by the Technical Team and presented in a summary of findings table.

513 Two people will rate the certainty of evidence for each outcome separately, and if they have different
514 opinions, they will discuss until they agree. If agreeing on the GRADE rating is too difficult, they
515 will consult with a third member of the team to decide.

516

517 GRADE results of a systematic review are usually presented in a table called “summary of findings”,
518 to make it easier for the user to understand the overall review results quickly. The information to be
519 included in the summary of findings tables for each outcome includes:

520

- 521 • The number of trials and the number of participants included in the analysis.
- 522 • The estimated effect (measured using either the mean difference or the standardised mean
523 difference) and 95% confidence interval.
- 524 • The overall GRADE certainty of evidence rating (high, moderate, low or very low) with an
525 explanation for this rating.
- 526 • Plain language summary explaining what the GRADE rating means.

527

528 The GRADEpro GDT software (73) will be used to create the summary of findings tables. If it is not
529 possible to complete a meta-analysis. In that case, we will present a narrative description of the
530 effects in the summary of findings table and rate the certainty of evidence using alternative methods
531 recommended when an effect estimate is not available (74).

532 **How will we consider equity in our review?**

533 We know that physical activity and exercise are beneficial for older adults’ physical and mental
534 health. However, these benefits may not be equally experienced by everyone, and we must explore
535 factors that could make accessing exercise more challenging for some people. For example, the
536 number of people who engage in enough exercise varies based on specific factors such as sex/gender,
537 socioeconomic status, and race/ethnicity (75–77). These factors may be considered as health
538 inequities, as they are inequalities between groups that are both unfair and avoidable (78).

539

540 Studies to date, exploring the effects of physical activity among older adults, have seldom explored
541 how the differences in the effects of these interventions are based on factors related to health inequity
542 (79,80). Therefore, within this systematic review (and systematic reviews in general), it is important
543 to accurately and consistently present equity-related data so that users of our review can interpret the
544 results within their specific context.

545

546 For this review, we will use the PRO-EDI (81–83) tool and guidance from the Cochrane Handbook
547 (84) to inform our consideration of health equity. Specifically, we will:

548

- 549 • Extract information from the included trials related to participant characteristics that may
550 contribute to inequitable access to the intervention.
- 551 • Report this information in a participant characteristics table [57], including information about
552 the people we would expect to see in the studies, and data reflecting the people who took part
553 in the studies.
- 554 • Include information in the summary of findings table related to equity, outlining the
555 populations to whom the certainty of evidence assessment applies (and may not apply).
- 556 • Conduct several subgroup analyses related to factors that are known to contribute to
557 inequitable access to exercise interventions for older adults, including sex/gender,
558 disability/presence of health conditions, and location (low, middle and high income
559 countries).
- 560 • Interpret the findings and applicability of the review results related to health equity in the
561 discussion section.

562 **DISCUSSION**

563 This review is being produced as an output from The People's Review project (1). We propose here
564 the methods for a systematic review conducted by the public about a topic chosen by the public,
565 investigating whether resistance training makes a difference to quality of life or heart health
566 compared to aerobic exercise, for older adults (over the age of 50 years). To the best of our
567 knowledge, no high-quality previous systematic review has explored this topic allowing such level of
568 public participation in the planning (including the elaboration of this protocol) and conduction of the
569 review. We hope that this review will be of use to people making decisions about engaging in
570 different types of exercise in their later years, including healthcare professionals supporting older
571 adults in practice, researchers, policymakers recommending guidelines and policies about older adult
572 healthcare services and resources, and funders of programs and resources.

573

574 There is growing support for members of the public to be involved in health research, including
575 systematic reviews (85–88), with a positive impact for everyone involved, including members of the
576 public, researchers, and healthcare professionals alike (85,89–91). We aim to produce a high-quality
577 review, co-created with the public, and support the public's understanding of systematic reviews and
578 their importance. We hope that our review will encourage other review authors to consider including
579 patient and public members in the review process and consider using The People's Review method as
580 a new way of involving people in health research. We will report the findings from The People's
581 Review in future publications.

582

583 This protocol has several strengths, including that it follows best practice guidelines for systematic
584 reviews about healthcare interventions (92,93) and that it actively involves the public throughout the
585 whole review process. However, as with all research, this review may have some limitations.

586

587 One scientific limitation of this review is that there are many ways to measure heart health, and
588 functional fitness is only one (albeit important) measure of heart health. However, this review is
589 being led by the public, who considered this as the most important outcome. Future reviews may
590 consider exploring other clinically important heart health measures, including blood pressure
591 changes, changes in heart health, cholesterol level or other measures of fitness. Another limitation is
592 that we are using the original Risk of Bias assessment (55). When we began planning how we would
593 include the public in risk of bias assessment, we made the decision that this was the most accessible
594 and easy-to-use version at the time. There is now an updated risk of bias (ROB-2) tool (94) that
595 could be considered in the future.

596

597 **Supplementary Information**

598 S1: Search Strategy

599 S2: PRISMA-P Checklist

600 S3: Competing interests for the group author The People

601

602 **DECLARATIONS**

603 **Authors contributions**

604 **Conceptualization:** ÉQ, LB, PL, KM, CN, DM, SMH, The People **Data curation:** ÉQ

605 **Methodology:** ÉQ, PL, KMSR, ST, CN, DM, SMH, The People **Project administration:** ÉQ, SMH

606 **Supervision:** CN, DM, SMH **Writing – original draft:** ÉQ **Writing – review & editing:** ÉQ, LB,

607 PL, KM, KMSR, CY, DCS, MS, JH, ST, CN, DM, SMH, The People

608

609 **Funding**

610 The People’s Review is funded by the Health Research Board (Ireland) (ESI-2021-001) and the HSC

611 Research and Development Division of the Public Health Agency (Northern Ireland) through

612 Evidence Synthesis Ireland and Cochrane Ireland. Éle Quinn’s PhD studentship is funded by the
613 College of Medicine, Nursing and Health Sciences, University of Galway, Ireland, through Evidence
614 Synthesis Ireland. Laura Bosner is supported by an Evidence Synthesis Ireland Summer Studentship
615 2025.

616

617 **Data availability**

618 Not applicable.

619

620 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

621 Ethics approval is not required for a systematic review. However, we have received ethical approval
622 from the University of Galway Research Ethics Committee (2023.06.012) to involve the public in
623 The People's Review.

624

625 **Competing interest**

626 ÉQ, LB, PL, CY, DS, MS, JH, ST, CN, and SMH have no competing interests to declare. DM is a
627 founding Editor-in-Chief of the journal. KMSUR is an Associate Editor of the journal. Competing
628 interests for members of the group author ‘The People’ are listed in Supplementary Material 3.

629

630 **Acknowledgements**

631 We want to thank The People's Review Steering Group for their commitment to The People's
632 Review. We would also like to thank the team at Cochrane Crowd and Metaxis (Anna Noel-Storr,
633 Gordon Dooley, and David Anstee) for their support in facilitating public involvement in this
634 protocol. ‘The People’ are listed as a group author on this protocol. The People is made up of the
635 following individuals: Oscar Soden, Christian Cortés Armijo, Paul K Bateman, Mehram Khaiser,
636 Jhoselin Marian Castro Rodriguez, Pareekshith Hireallur Lohithaswa, Stella Hassan, Kavessh

637 Vandaiyar, V Nikhila Priya, Dr. Sushant Swaroop Das, Fredrik Nyman, Shannon Cheng, Ana Laura
638 Afonso Garcia, Virgilio Blandon, Johanna Pope, Gerard Mangan, Naam Kadhim, Jehath Syed,
639 Rebecca M. Lane, Sri Harsha Chalasani, Belén Morales Franco, Hanadi H. Almintish, Kirthana Nair,
640 Aisha Elnagi, Barbara Molony-Oates, Diarmuid Verrier, Ivana Turudic, Raiza Rai, Abhijit Dutta,
641 Ulrich Schmitz, Mahmoud Rashad Kamal, Anup Rai, Aduak Israel Bassey, Rayan Haidar, Thora El-
642 Sayed, Skarlet Marcell Vásquez, Megha Bhattacharyya, Ali Abud, Jakub Ruszkowski, Simone Ryan,
643 Aliasghar Fakhri-Demeshghieh, Declan Devane, Olivia Smith, Elaine Lorigan McSweeney, Aishath
644 Mala, Nirvi Sharma, Wajida Perveen, Elizabeth Deane McCarthy, Johannes Wagner, Anthony
645 Rimmer, Bláthnaid Quinn, Mónica Rosalía Loera Pulido, Dr. Nikhil Sisodiya, Mirza Ammar Arshad,
646 Eugene Farrell, Maria Elena Asdrubali, Alaa AM Osman, Kapil Paiwal, Gursimer Jeet, Simone
647 Lepage, Mahla Azizzadeh Herozi, Lasse Østengaard, Richard Lohmann, Radheshyam Meher, Louise
648 van der Merwe, Shirley Hall, Aragaw Hamza Yimer, Dr Kanimozhi V, Neil Canham, Dr Orton
649 Lungu, Laura Aparecida Martins Albino, Chang Helly, Braa Bushra Gorani Hamid, Ashraf Sadeq
650 Nasser Yahya Qadesh, Fábio André Miranda Viana, Pierpaolo Giordano, Abir Romdhani, Sameeksha
651 Shetty, Jose D. Cruz-Cuevas, Paul Owusu, Amanda Doherty-Kirby, Gary Hoang, Kin Fung SO, Dr.
652 Denny Mathew John, Ayman Nadeem, Hariklia Nguyen, Mengqi Li, Merlyn Joseph Stalin Vellalar,
653 Yuna Kato, Haoling Wang, Devarajulu Reddy Sirasanambati, Michelle I M Paynter, Akuma
654 Ifeanyichukwu, Anuj Kumar Pandey, Agnes Falconer, Amit Ahuja, Muhammad Zohaib, Basavaraj
655 Poojar, Hosna Khazaei, Karla Elizabeth Duque Jacome, Holly Southall, Sunjuri Sun, Federico
656 Capriles, Lyria Arcari, Annemarie Sheehan, Alexia Jeayes, Karan Sethi, M. Dulce Estêvão, Dejana
657 Krajacic, Mohammed S. Abujayyab, Nicole Askin, Amanda de Carvalho Robaina, Jen Smith, Shruti
658 Bora, Deepak Singh-Ranger, Adi Zeba, Giovana Vesentini, Dr. Orla Mooney, Christopher James
659 Graham, Kim Locke, Jeanna Pillainayagam, Dr Abdul Shakoor, Qamar Uz Zaman Khan, Marwa
660 Yahia Elbasosy, Emily Shepherd, Marina Maria Manea, Danielle Lawrence, Cristhian Gonzalo
661 Aspiazu-Briones, Quynh Thuong Huynh, Zarah Janda, Jesus Salvador Garcia Lopez, Tint Hla Hla

662 Htoo, A Dennington-Price, Patrick De Neve, Ahmadu Inuwa, Thu-Huong Nguyen, Manon Hubert,
663 Richard Sinert, DO, Lenora Murphy, Christopher W. Roche, Conor McKinney, Aidan Quinn,
664 Michael-Dharma Irwin, Dr. Adedoyin Adeosun, Chandan Kumar, Mai Babenko, Fatma Alagelli,
665 Moni Choudhury, Mona Lee, Aswathi Surendran, Renee Jarrett, MPH, Williams, R.J.C., Zeev
666 Konstantin G. Gurevich, Therese Kristine Dalsbø, Oluwaseun Abigail Newton, Alice Fognani,
667 Feargal Quinn, Ciara Smith, Janani Surya Ravichandran, Oyewale Johnson Akande, Evangelia
668 Papadimou, Anwyn Johnson, Aswin K Mohan, Parichehr Hayatdavoudi, Brenda Golden, Dr.
669 Srikanth S., Shahd Ashraf Izzeldin Abdalla, Alaa Mohamed, Rose Nasser, João Morgadinho,
670 Stephanie Skeffington, Matthieu Gaiotti-Gras, Lucas HCC Santos, April English, Eliane Denise
671 Bahbouth, Yasmine Ahmed Mourad Asaad, Eva O'Byrne, Neha Singh, Syeda Safura Sultana, Marci
672 Kay Livingston, Jenny Bui, Adeola Ajayi, Faith Armitage, Silvia Maria Martins Bernardo, Grace
673 Walsh and Omar Alhaman. All authors listed on this protocol have provided consent for their names
674 to be listed, have reviewed or edited the manuscript, thereby complying with the International
675 Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) authorship guidance (95).

676 **References**

- 677 1. Quinn É, Dawson S, Holt J, Hossain S, Logullo P, O'Brien A, et al. The People's Review
678 protocol: planning an innovative study powered by the public. *Res Involv Engagem.*
679 2025;11:28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-025-00682-7>
- 680 2. Qiu S, Cai X, Liu J, Yang B, Sun Z, Zügel M, et al. Association Between Cardiorespiratory
681 Fitness and Risk of Heart Failure: A Meta-Analysis. *J Card Fail.* 2019;25:537–44.
682 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cardfail.2019.04.008>
- 683 3. Qiu S, Cai X, Yang B, Du Z, Cai M, Sun Z, et al. Association Between Cardiorespiratory
684 Fitness and Risk of Type 2 Diabetes: A Meta-Analysis. *Obesity.* 2019;27:315–
685 24. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oby.22368>
- 686 4. Chu DJ, Al Rifai M, Virani SS, Brawner CA, Nasir K, Al-Mallah MH. The relationship
687 between cardiorespiratory fitness, cardiovascular risk factors and atherosclerosis.
688 *Atherosclerosis.* 2020;304:44–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2020.04.019>
- 689 5. Lee J, Chen B, Kohl HW, Barlow CE, Lee C do, Radford NB, et al. The association of
690 midlife cardiorespiratory fitness with later life carotid atherosclerosis: Cooper Center
691 Longitudinal Study. *Atherosclerosis.* 2019;282:137–42.
692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2019.01.009>
- 693 6. The World Health Organization. World Report on Ageing and Health. World Health
694 Organization; 2015. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241565042>

- 695 7. Daskalopoulou C, Stubbs B, Kralj C, Koukounari A, Prince M, Prina AM. Physical activity
696 and healthy ageing: A systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal cohort studies.
697 *Ageing Res Rev.* 2017;38:6–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2017.06.003>
- 698 8. Moreno-Agostino D, Daskalopoulou C, Wu Y-T, Koukounari A, Haro JM, Tyrovolas S, et al.
699 The impact of physical activity on healthy ageing trajectories: evidence from eight cohort
700 studies. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act.* 2020;17:92. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-020-00995-8>
- 701 9. Chodzko-Zajko WJ, Proctor DN, Fiatarone Singh MA, Minson CT, Nigg CR, Salem GJ, et
702 al. Exercise and Physical Activity for Older Adults. *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* 2009;41:1510–30.
703 <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0b013e3181a0c95c>
- 704 10. Izquierdo M, Merchant RA, Morley JE, Anker SD, Aprahamian I, Arai H, et al. International
705 Exercise Recommendations in Older Adults (ICFSR): Expert Consensus Guidelines. *J Nutr*
706 *Health Aging.* 2021;25:824–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12603-021-1665-8>
- 707 11. Izquierdo M, de Souto Barreto P, Arai H, Bischoff-Ferrari HA, Cadore EL, Cesari M, et al.
708 Global consensus on optimal exercise recommendations for enhancing healthy longevity in
709 older adults (ICFSR). *J Nutr Health Aging.* 2025;29:100401.
710 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnha.2024.100401>
- 711 12. The World Health Organization. WHO Guidelines on Physical Activity and Sedentary
712 Behaviour. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2020.
713 <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240015128>. Accessed 28 Aug 2025.
- 714 13. Nelson M, Rejeski W, Blair S, Duncan P, Judge J, King A, et al. Physical Activity and Public
715 Health in Older Adults: Recommendation From the American College of Sports Medicine
716 and the American Heart Association. *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* 2007;116:1094–105.
717 <https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0b013e3180616aa2>
- 718 14. Ashton RE, Tew GA, Aning JJ, Gilbert SE, Lewis L, Saxton JM. Effects of short-term,
719 medium-term and long-term resistance exercise training on cardiometabolic health outcomes
720 in adults: systematic review with meta-analysis. *Br J Sports Med.* 2020;54:341–8.
721 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2017-098970>
- 722 15. Banks NF, Rogers EM, Stanhewicz AE, Whitaker KM, Jenkins NDM. Resistance exercise
723 lowers blood pressure and improves vascular endothelial function in individuals with
724 elevated blood pressure or stage-1 hypertension. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol.*
725 2024;326:H256–69. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00386.2023>
- 726 16. Lopes S, Afreixo V, Teixeira M, Garcia C, Leitão C, Gouveia M, et al. Exercise training
727 reduces arterial stiffness in adults with hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J*
728 *Hypertens.* 2021;39:214. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HJH.0000000000002619>
- 729 17. Lovell DI, Cuneo R, Gass GC. Strength Training Improves Submaximum Cardiovascular
730 performance in Older Men. *J Geriatr Phys Ther.* 2009;32:117.
731 <https://doi.org/10.1519/00139143-200932030-00007>
- 732 18. Hunter GR, McCarthy JP, Bamman MM. Effects of resistance training on older adults. *Sports*
733 *Med.* 2004;34:329–48. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200434050-00005>
- 734 19. Paluch AE, Boyer WR, Franklin BA, Laddu D, Lobelo F, Lee D, et al. Resistance Exercise
735 Training in Individuals With and Without Cardiovascular Disease: 2023 Update: A Scientific
736 Statement From the American Heart Association. *Circulation.* 2024;149:217–31.
737 <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000001189>
- 738 20. Smart TFF, Doleman B, Hatt J, Paul M, Toft S, Lund JN, et al. The role of resistance exercise
739 training for improving cardiorespiratory fitness in healthy older adults: A systematic review
740 and meta-Analysis. *Age Ageing.* 2022;51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afac143>
- 741 21. Hart PD, Buck DJ. The effect of resistance training on health-related quality of life in older
742 adults: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Health Promot Perspect.* 2019;9:1–12.
743 <https://doi.org/10.15171/hpp.2019.01>

- 744 22. An J, Su Z, Meng S. Effect of aerobic training versus resistance training for improving
745 cardiorespiratory fitness and body composition in middle-aged to older adults: A systematic
746 review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr.*
747 2024;126:105530. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2024.105530>
- 748 23. Frontera WR, Meredith CN, O'Reilly KP, Evans WJ. Strength training and determinants of
749 VO₂max in older men. *Journal of Applied Physiology. J Appl Physiol.* 1990;68:329–33.
750 <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappl.1990.68.1.329>
- 751 24. Hepple RT, Mackinnon SLM, Thomas SG, Goodman JM, Plyley MJ. Quantitating the
752 capillary supply and the response to resistance training in older men. *Pfluegers Arch.*
753 1996;433:238–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004240050273>
- 754 25. Phillips B, Williams J, Atherton P, Smith K, Hildebrandt W, Rankin D, et al. Resistance
755 exercise training improves age-related declines in leg vascular conductance and rejuvenates
756 acute leg blood flow responses to feeding and exercise. *J Appl Physiol.* 2012;112:347–53.
757 <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappphysiol.01031.2011>
- 758 26. Wewege MA, Desai I, Honey C, Coorie B, Jones MD, Clifford BK, et al. The Effect of
759 Resistance Training in Healthy Adults on Body Fat Percentage, Fat Mass and Visceral Fat: A
760 Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Sports Med.* 2022;52:287–300.
761 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-021-01562-2>
- 762 27. Bårdstu HB, Andersen V, Fimland MS, Aasdahl L, Raastad T, Cumming KT, et al.
763 Effectiveness of a resistance training program on physical function, muscle strength, and
764 body composition in community-dwelling older adults receiving home care: a cluster-
765 randomized controlled trial. *Eur Rev Aging Phys Act.* 2020;17:11.
766 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11556-020-00243-9>
- 767 28. Papa EV, Dong X, Hassan M. Resistance training for activity limitations in older adults with
768 skeletal muscle function deficits: a systematic review. *Clin Interv Aging.* 2017;12:955–
769 <https://doi.org/10.2147/CIA.S104674>
- 770 29. Sherrington C, Fairhall N, Kwok W, Wallbank G, Tiedemann A, Michaleff ZA, et al.
771 Evidence on physical activity and falls prevention for people aged 65+ years: systematic
772 review to inform the WHO guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. *Int J*
773 *Behav Nutr Phys Act.* 2020;17:144. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-020-01041-3>
- 774 30. Khodadad Kashi S, Mirzazadeh ZS, Saatchian V. A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of
775 Resistance Training on Quality of Life, Depression, Muscle Strength, and Functional
776 Exercise Capacity in Older Adults Aged 60 Years or More. *Biol Res Nurs.* 2023;25:88–106.
777 <https://doi.org/10.1177/10998004221120945>
- 778 31. Cunha PM, Werneck AO, Santos L dos, Oliveira MD, Zou L, Schuch FB, et al. Can
779 resistance training improve mental health outcomes in older adults? A systematic review and
780 meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Psychiatry Res.* 2024;333:115746.
781 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2024.115746>
- 782 32. Herring MP, Meyer JD. Resistance exercise for anxiety and depression: efficacy and
783 plausible mechanisms. *Trends Mol Med.* 2024;30:204–6.
784 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmed.2023.11.016>
- 785 33. Marquez DX, Aguiñaga S, Vásquez PM, Conroy DE, Erickson KI, Hillman C, et al. A
786 systematic review of physical activity and quality of life and well-being. *Transl Behav Med.*
787 2020;10:1098–109. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tbm/ibz198>
- 788 34. Coelho-Junior H, Marzetti E, Calvani R, Picca A, Arai H, Uchida M. Resistance training
789 improves cognitive function in older adults with different cognitive status: a systematic
790 review and Meta-analysis. *Aging Ment Health.* 2022;26:213–24.
791 <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2020.1857691>

- 792 35. Moher D, Shamseer L, Clarke M, Ghersi D, Liberati A, Petticrew M, et al. Preferred
793 reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015
794 statement. *Syst Rev*. 2015;4:1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2046-4053-4-1>
- 795 36. Chandler J, Cumpston M, Thomas M, Higgins JP, Deeks J, Clarke M. Chapter I:
796 Introduction. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 63
797 (updated February 2022). Cochrane; 2022 www.training.cochrane.org/handbook. Accessed 1
798 June 2023.
- 799 37. Lawrence LM, Singleton JF. What Do We Mean by Older Adult and Physical Activity?
800 Reviewing the Use of These Terms in Recent Research. *Activ Adapt Aging*. 2017; 41:22–46.
801 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01924788.2016.1272391>
- 802 38. Villalobos Dint rans P, Izquierdo C, Guzmán R, Gálvez MJ, Santander S. Defining ‘older
803 people’ in Chile: challenges in planning policies for ageing populations. *Health Policy and*
804 *Plan*. 2020;35:1347–53. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czaa113>
- 805 39. UNHCR (The UN Refugee Agency). Older
806 persons.<https://emergency.unhcr.org/protection/persons-risk/older-persons>. Accessed 31 July
807 2025
- 808 40. Kowal P, Kowal EJ. Definition of an older person. Proposed working definition of an older
809 person in Africa for the MDS Project. 2001. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.5188.9286>
- 810 41. WHOQOL: Measuring Quality of Life| The World Health Organization.
811 <https://www.who.int/tools/whoqol> Accessed 31 July 2025
- 812 42. Ware JE, Kosinski M, Bjorner JB, Turner-Bowker DM, Gandek B, Maruish ME. User’s
813 manual for the SF-36v2TM health survey. 2nd ed. Lincoln: Quality Metric
814 Incorporated;2007.
- 815 43. Ware JE, Sherbourne CD. The MOS 36-item short-form health survey (SF-36). Conceptual
816 framework and item selection. *Med Care*. 1992;30:473–83.
- 817 44. EuroQol Research Foundation. EQ-5D-3L User Guide. 2018.
818 <https://euroqol.org/publications/user-guides>.
- 819 45. The World Health Organization. WHOQOL User Manual. Geneva: World Health
820 Organization; 1998
- 821 46. The American Thoracic Society (ATS). Guidelines for the Six-Minute Walk Test. *Am J*
822 *Respir Crit Care Med*. American Thoracic Society - AJRCCM; 2002;166:111–7.
823 <https://doi.org/10.1164/ajrccm.166.1.at1102>
- 824 47. Medrano-Ureña M del R, Ortega-Ruiz R, Benítez-Sillero J de D. Physical Fitness, Exercise
825 Self-Efficacy, and Quality of Life in Adulthood: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res*
826 *Public Health*. 2020;17:6343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17176343>
- 827 48. Haddaway NR, Rethlefsen ML, Davies M, Glanville J, McGowan B, Nyhan K, et al.
828 suggested data structure for transparent and repeatable reporting of bibliographic searching.
829 *Campbell Syst Rev*. 2022;18:e1288. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cl2.1288>
- 830 49. McGowan J, Sampson M, Salzwedel DM, Cogo E, Foerster V, Lefebvre C. PRESS Peer
831 Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Statement. *J Clin Epidemiol*.
832 2016;75:40–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.01.021>
- 833 50. Wright JM, Jones D. Search strategies to investigate decision making by older adults and
834 appraisal by GPs following cancer symptoms. University of Leeds; 2021.
835 <https://doi.org/10.5518/1034>
- 836 51. Glanville J, Kotas E, Featherstone R, Dooley G. Which are the most sensitive search filters to
837 identify randomized controlled trials in MEDLINE? *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2020;108:556–63.
838 <https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2020.912>
- 839 52. Ouzzani M, Hammady H, Fedorowicz Z, Elmagarmid A. Rayyan—a web and mobile app for
840 systematic reviews. *Syst Rev* 2016;5(1):1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-016-0384-4>

- 841 53. Noel-Storr A, Dooley G, Elliott J, Steele E, Shemilt I, Mavergames C, et al. An evaluation of
842 Cochrane Crowd found that crowdsourcing produced accurate results in identifying
843 randomized trials. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021;133:130–9.
844 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.01.006>
- 845 54. Noel-Storr A, Dooley G, Affengruber L, Gartlehner G. Citation screening using
846 crowdsourcing and machine learning produced accurate results: Evaluation of Cochrane’s
847 modified Screen4Me service. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021;130:23–31.
848 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.09.024>
- 849 55. Higgins JPT, Altman DG, Gøtzsche PC, Jüni P, Moher D, Oxman AD, et al. The Cochrane
850 Collaboration’s tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*;
851 2011;343:d59282011. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d5928>
- 852 56. Higgins JPT, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Chapter 16: Special topics in statistics. *Cochrane*
853 *Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* Version 510. 2011. www.cochrane914
854 handbook.org.
- 855 57. Campbell M, McKenzie JE, Sowden A, Katikireddi SV, Brennan SE, Ellis S, et al. Synthesis
856 without meta-analysis (SWiM) in systematic reviews: reporting guideline. *BMJ*.
857 2020;368:l6890. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l6890>
- 858 58. Higgins JPT, Eldridge S, Li T. Chapter 23: Including variants on randomized trials. *Cochrane*
859 *Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 65. Cochrane; 2024.
860 cochrane.org/handbook
- 861 59. Jakobsen JC, Gluud C, Wetterslev J, Winkel P. When and how should multiple imputation be
862 used for handling missing data in randomised clinical trials - a practical guide with
863 flowcharts. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2017;17:162. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0442-1)
864 [0442-1](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0442-1)
- 865 60. Furukawa TA, Barbui C, Cipriani A, Brambilla P, Watanabe N. Imputing missing standard
866 deviations in meta-analyses can provide accurate results. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2006;59:7–10.
867 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2005.06.006>
- 868 61. Deeks J, Higgins J, Altman DG, McKenzie JE, Veroniki A-A. Chapter 10: Analysing data
869 and undertaking meta-analyses. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*
870 version 65. Cochrane; 2024. cochrane.org/handbook
- 871 62. Page M, Higgins J, Sterne J. Chapter 13: Assessing risk of bias due to missing evidence in a
872 meta-analysis. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 65.
873 Cochrane; 2024. cochrane.org/handbook
- 874 63. Peters JL, Sutton AJ, Jones DR, Abrams KR, Rushton L. Contour-enhanced meta-analysis
875 funnel plots help distinguish publication bias from other causes of asymmetry. *J Clin*
876 *Epidemiol*. 2008;61:991–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2007.11.010>
- 877 64. Sterne JAC, Sutton AJ, Ioannidis JPA, Terrin N, Jones DR, Lau J, et al. Recommendations
878 for examining and interpreting funnel plot asymmetry in meta-analyses of randomised
879 controlled trials. *BMJ*. 2011;343:d4002. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d4002>
- 880 65. Egger M, Smith GD, Schneider M, Minder C. Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple,
881 graphical test. *BMJ*. 1997;315:629–34. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.315.7109.629>
- 882 66. Fekete JT, Györfy B. MetaAnalysisOnline.com: Web-Based Tool for the Rapid Meta-
883 Analysis of Clinical and Epidemiological Studies. *J Med Internet Res*. 2025;27:e64016.
884 <https://doi.org/10.2196/64016>
- 885 67. Guyatt G, Agoritsas T, Brignardello-Petersen R, Mustafa RA, Rylance J, Foroutan F, et al.
886 Core GRADE 1: overview of the Core GRADE approach. *BMJ*. 2025;389:e081903.
887 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-081903>
- 888 68. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, Kunz R, Vist G, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1.
889 Introduction—GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*.
890 2011;64:383–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.04.026>

- 891 69. Guyatt G, Wang Y, Eachempati P, Iorio A, Murad MH, Hultcrantz M, et al. Core GRADE 4:
892 rating certainty of evidence—risk of bias, publication bias, and reasons for rating up
893 certainty. *BMJ*. 2025;389:e083864. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-083864>
- 894 70. Guyatt G, Zeng L, Brignardello-Petersen R, Prasad M, Beer HD, Murad MH, et al. Core
895 GRADE 2: choosing the target of certainty rating and assessing imprecision. *BMJ*.
896 2025;389:e081904. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-081904>
- 897 71. Guyatt G, Iorio A, Beer HD, Owen A, Agoritsas T, Murad MH, et al. Core GRADE 5: rating
898 certainty of evidence—assessing indirectness. *BMJ*. 2025;389:e083865.
899 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-083865>
- 900 72. Guyatt G, Schandelmaier S, Brignardello-Petersen R, Beer HD, Prasad M, Murad MH, et al.
901 Core GRADE 3: rating certainty of evidence—assessing inconsistency. *BMJ*.
902 2025;389:e081905. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-081905>
- 903 73. GRADEpro. <https://www.gradepro.org/>. Accessed 16 June 2025
- 904 74. Murad MH, Mustafa RA, Schünemann HJ, Sultan S, Santesso N. Rating the certainty in
905 evidence in the absence of a single estimate of effect. *Evid Based Med*. 2017;22:85–7.
906 <https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmed-2017-110668>
- 907 75. Guthold R, Stevens GA, Riley LM, Bull FC. Worldwide trends in insufficient physical
908 activity from 2001 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 358 population-based surveys with 1·9
909 million participants. *The Lancet Global Health*. 2018;6:e1077–86.
910 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30357-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30357-7)
- 911 76. O’Donoghue G, Kennedy A, Puggina A, Aleksovska K, Buck C, Burns C, et al. Socio
912 economic determinants of physical activity across the life course: A “DEterminants of Diet
913 and Physical ACTivity” (DEDIPAC) umbrella literature review. *PLOS ONE*.
914 2018;13:e0190737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0190737>
- 915 77. SFM C, Van Cauwenberg J, Maenhout L, Cardon G, Lambert EV, Van Dyck D. Inequality
916 in physical activity, global trends by income inequality and gender in adults. *Int J Behav Nutr
917 Phys Act*. 2020;17:142. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-020-01039-x>
- 918 78. Welch V, Dewidar O, Tanjong Ghogomu E, Abdisalam S, Al Ameer A, Barbeau VI, et al.
919 How effects on health equity are assessed in systematic reviews of interventions. *Cochrane
920 Database Syst Rev*. 2022;2022:MR000028.
921 <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.MR000028.pub3>
- 922 79. Czwikla G, Boen F, Cook DG, de Jong J, Harris T, Hilz LK, et al. Equity-specific effects of
923 interventions to promote physical activity among middle-aged and older adults: results from
924 applying a novel equity-specific re-analysis strategy. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2021;18:65.
925 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-021-01131-w>
- 926 80. Lehne G, Bolte G. Impact of universal interventions on social inequalities in physical activity
927 among older adults: an equity-focused systematic review. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*.
928 2017;14:20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-017-0472-4>
- 929 81. PRO EDI interpretation guidance. 2024. [https://www.trialforge.org/trial-diversity/pro-edi997-
930 improving-how-equity-diversity-and-inclusion-is-handled-in-evidence-synthesis/](https://www.trialforge.org/trial-diversity/pro-edi997-improving-how-equity-diversity-and-inclusion-is-handled-in-evidence-synthesis/). Accessed
931 29 May 2025.
- 932 82. PRO EDI participant characteristics table. 2024. [https://www.trialforge.org/trial1000-
933 diversity/pro-edi-improving-how-equity-diversity-and-inclusion-is-handled-in-evidence1001-
934 synthesis/](https://www.trialforge.org/trial1000-diversity/pro-edi-improving-how-equity-diversity-and-inclusion-is-handled-in-evidence1001-synthesis/). Accessed 29 Aug 2025.
- 935 83. Treweek S, Devane D, Welch V, Petkovic J, Tugwell P, Saif-Ur-Rahman KM, et al. PRO
936 EDI -- a tool to help systematic reviewers make equity, diversity and inclusion assessments.
937 [https://www.authorea.com/users/793069/articles/1319406-pro-edi-a-tool-to-help-
938 systematic1005reviewers-make-equity-diversity-and-
939 inclusion1006assessments?commit=8eed6c50bef7b9fd6f4213e47f2e15a7ccb69f9f](https://www.authorea.com/users/793069/articles/1319406-pro-edi-a-tool-to-help-systematic1005reviewers-make-equity-diversity-and-inclusion1006assessments?commit=8eed6c50bef7b9fd6f4213e47f2e15a7ccb69f9f). Accessed
940 29 Aug 2025.

- 941 84. Welch V, Petkovic J, Jull J, Hartling L, Klassen T, Kristjansson E, et al. Chapter 16: Equity
942 and specific populations. Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions
943 version 65. Cochrane; 2024. [cochrane.org/handbook](https://www.cochrane.org/handbook)
- 944 85. Agyei-Manu E, Atkins N, Lee B, Rostron J, Dozier M, Smith M, et al. The benefits,
945 challenges, and best practice for patient and public involvement in evidence synthesis: A
946 systematic review and thematic synthesis. *Health Expect*. 2023;
947 <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.13787>
- 948 86. Cochrane. Cochrane consumer engagement and involvement framework to 2027. 2022.
949 [https://consumers.cochrane.org/sites/consumers.cochrane.org/files/uploads/inline1016files/C](https://consumers.cochrane.org/sites/consumers.cochrane.org/files/uploads/inline1016files/Cochrane%20consumer%20engagement%20and%20involvement%20framework%20to%202027_0.pdf)
950 [ochrane%20consumer%20engagement%20and%20involvement%20framework%20to%2020](https://consumers.cochrane.org/sites/consumers.cochrane.org/files/uploads/inline1016files/Cochrane%20consumer%20engagement%20and%20involvement%20framework%20to%202027_0.pdf)
951 [27_0.pdf](https://consumers.cochrane.org/sites/consumers.cochrane.org/files/uploads/inline1016files/Cochrane%20consumer%20engagement%20and%20involvement%20framework%20to%202027_0.pdf). Accessed 1 June 2023
- 952 87. Global Commission on Evidence to Address Societal Challenges. The Evidence Commission
953 report: A wake-up call and path forward for decisionmakers, evidence intermediaries, and
954 impact-oriented evidence producers. Hamilton: McMaster Health Forum;2022.
955 <https://www.mcmasterforum.org/networks/evidence-commission>. Accessed 1 June 2023
- 956 88. Pollock A, Campbell P, Struthers C, Synnot A, Nunn J, Hill S, et al. Development of the
957 ACTIVE framework to describe stakeholder involvement in systematic reviews. *J Health*
958 *Serv Res Policy*. 2019;24:245–55. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1355819619841647>
- 959 89. Hemphill R, Forsythe LP, Heckert AL, Amolegbe A, Maurer M, Carman KL, et al. What
960 motivates patients and caregivers to engage in health research and how engagement affects
961 their lives: Qualitative survey findings. *Health Expect*. 2020;23:328–36.
962 <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12979>
- 963 90. Lauzon-Schnittka J, Audette-Chapdelaine S, Boutin D, Wilhelmy C, Auger A-M, Brodeur M.
964 The experience of patient partners in research: a qualitative systematic review and thematic
965 synthesis. *Res Involv Engagem*. 2022;8:1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-022-00388-0>
- 966 91. Røssvoll TB, Liabo K, Hanssen TA, Rosenvinge JH, Sundkvist E, Pettersen G. What
967 motivates public collaborators to become and stay involved in health research? *Res Involv*
968 *Engagem*. 2024;10:1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-024-00555-5>
- 969 92. Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, et al. Cochrane Handbook
970 for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 6.5. Cochrane; 2024.
971 www.cochrane.org/handbook
- 972 93. Higgins J, Lasserson T, Thomas J, Flemyng E, Churchill R. Methodological Expectations of
973 Cochrane Intervention Reviews (MECIR). 2023. <https://community.cochrane.org/mecir1042>
974 manual
- 975 94. Flemyng E, Moore TH, Boutron I, Higgins JP, Hróbjartsson A, Nejtgaard CH, et al. Using
976 Risk of Bias 2 to assess results from randomised controlled trials: guidance from Cochrane.
977 *BMJ Evid Based Med*. 2023; <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2022-112102>
- 978 95. International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE). Recommendations for the
979 Conduct, Reporting, Editing, and Publication of Scholarly Work in Medical Journals. 2025.
980 [https://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-](https://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-role1050of-authors-and-contributors.html)
981 [role1050of-authors-and-contributors.html](https://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-role1050of-authors-and-contributors.html). Accessed 23 Aug 2025
- 982